

CAPITAL STRUCTURE BEFORE AND AFTER MERGER AND ACQUISITION: BANKING INDUSTRY IN MALAYSIA

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ABSTRACT: *During the Asian financial crisis in year 1997, countries under International Monetary Fund (IMF) programmes are required to close down the small and weakest banking institutions. However, Malaysia government denied and initiated a robust bank merger programme to restructure all the fifty four financial institutions into ten anchor banks in year 1999. By the end of 2011, there were only eight anchor banks in Malaysia. Today, Malaysian Government still encourages companies in Malaysia to participate in the merger and acquisition activities. Previously, many studies were done according this issue by using Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA). However, the impact of merger and acquisition of Malaysian Bank is still vague. Hence, this paper attempts to examine the impact of merger and acquisition of Malaysian bank by using capital structure. This paper focuses on seven pairs of anchor banks which merged and acquired other minor banks in Malaysia from year 1999 until 2006. This paper uses descriptive statistic to compare the capital ratios and profitability ratios of 5 years before and after merger and acquisition to identify the impact. Besides, regression analysis used to determine the relationship of independents variables and dependent variables.*

The overall result of this study proved that merger and acquisition in Malaysian anchor banks do not significant increment the capital structure of bank. However, the result of ROA and ROE indicate performance of banks will improve after merger and acquisition. On the other hand, EPS indicate the shareholder's value will slightly diminished after the merger and acquisition. Moreover, the result in more attentive view (changes of capital structure and performance of each pair of bank) indicates not all bidders and targets will had better performance after the consolidation. This proved that merger and acquisition do not solely brought benefit to the bank and country's economy. The impact of merger and acquisition will affect by the bidder and target condition, economic condition and other external factors.

Background of the Study

Merger is a combination of two or more companies through the pooling of interests. The name of the company after merger can be a new company's name or follow either buyer or the seller company's name. Furthermore, an acquisition is one company taking over controlling interest in another company. The assets or the stock of the seller are purchased for cash and/or stock of the buyer. The buyer is definitely the dominant party in acquisition transactions. After acquisition, the seller company will no longer exist (Loong, 2008). Based on Thomson Reuters data, the total merger and acquisition in Malaysia was increased to US\$35.025 billion for the period from 1 Jan 2008, to 16 Dec 2008. Furthermore, Asian financial sector deal values totalled US\$27.7 billion for the first half of 2011, up to 39.6% from US\$19.8 billion in the same period last year. In Malaysia, a total of 18 financial services M&A deals in 2010 yielded a total value of US\$912 million, which is significantly less than 2009's total figure of US\$1.8 billion (Wong and Soo, 2011).

Merger and acquisition (M&A) activities in Malaysia obviously started in 1970's which were largely confined to oil palm and rubber plantation companies. The involvement

of foreign companies in the merger and acquisition activity was also noted to be quite significant especially in the plantation sector. In 1980's, process of merger of bank in Malaysia grew rapidly because of the economic recession in the mid of year 1980. This caused the number of local bank in Malaysia to reduce from eighty in the earliest of year 1980s to fifty four in the end of year 1990s. According to Bank Negara Malaysia (1999), the banking crisis in the mid-1980s caused a number of weak commercial banks and finance companies into insolvency and financial distress. These institutions were saddled with huge levels of nonperforming loans, over-lending to the property sector and neglected in share-based lending during the earlier boom years. Consequently, the financial company faced a huge loss. Central Bank of Malaysia had to implement a rescue scheme to maintain integrity of public savings and the stability of the financial system in Malaysia. The rescue scheme involved the Central Bank of Malaysia acquired shares in some of the commercial banks and the absorption of the assets and liabilities of the insolvent finance companies by stronger finance companies.

Furthermore, the Asian financial crisis in year 1990s caused the Central Bank of Malaysia to encourage merger and acquisition in Malaysian banking industry. According to Bala and Mohendran (2003), the initial recent merger in the Malaysia financial industry occurred in 1990 with the takeover of United Asian Bank by Bank of Commerce. This entity subsequently merged with Bank Bumiputra to form Bank Bumiputra Commerce on 1 October 1999. The second mergers saw the takeover of Kwong Yik Bank by Rashid Hussain Group in late 1996 to form RHB Bank. Subsequently, Sime Bank joined the RHB Group in June 1999.

After Asian financial crisis in year 1997, The International Monetary Fund (IMF) forced countries under their programmes such as Indonesia, Thailand and South Korea to reduce the number of banking institutions by effectively closing them down. However, Malaysia does not believe that the IMF's prescription of closing down the problematic bank is the way to solve the problem. This because the social costs involved in terms of dislocation of resources are high. Hence, Malaysian government decided to implement guided merger, with the central bank playing a proactive

role in solving the issues involved and the principle of fairness will be strictly applied to all parties in the merger (Hazlina, Zarehan and Muzlifah, 2010).

In order to ensure Malaysian local banks are able to compete in the global stage and achieve the economics of scale, the Central Bank of Malaysia proposed a major restructuring plan for its fifty-four domestic deposit-taking financial institutions to be consolidated into just ten institutions on February 2000. The ten anchor banks are show in Table 1. According to Ruby, Ariff and Michael (2007), merger plan in Malaysia banking industry was fundamentally desirable. This is because Malaysia had too many banks for a small economy, which proved by the very high banking density (total population divided by total number of bank branches) in this small economy. Besides, the World Trade Organization (WTO) also pressures to remove regulations that restrict entrance of foreign institutions into the local markets in Malaysia commence on year 2003. Hence, Central Bank of Malaysia would like to build strong local bank in order to compete globally (Hazlina, Zarehan and Muzlifah,2010).

Table 1- List of Anchor Bank in Malaysia

Anchor Banks	
1. Maybank Berhad	2. CIMB Berhad
3. Alliance Bank Malaysia Berhad	4. AmBank (M) Berhad
5. Affin Bank Berhad	6. Hong Leong Bank Berhad
7. Public Bank Berhad	8. RHB Bank Berhad
9. EON Bank Berhad	10. Southern Bank Berhad

(Source: Central Bank of Malaysia, 2003)

The Central Bank of Malaysia proposed the plan which allowed the ten anchor banks to form their own banking groups as to meet the minimum capital requirement of RM2 billion and minimum total assets of RM25 billion. As a result, by the end of year 2000, the domestic banking institutions controlled about 75% of banking sector in terms of total assets and total deposits (Ahmad and Murzali, 2008). Thus, according to Bank Negara Malaysia (2004), the operating cost of domestic banking institutions has declined from 41.2% in 2001 to 40.3% of total income in 2003.

Despite a more competitive environment, domestic banking institutions have been able to sustain their market share at 80%. The domestic banks commanded an 83% share of the outstanding loans to the small and medium enterprises, while their market share in the credit card business has increased from 46% in 2000 to 54% of total credit cards issued in 2003.

During year 2000s, the number of merger and acquisition activities in Malaysian banking industry increased gradually.

This is because the anchor bank started merged with other smaller banks in that period. By year 2006, the ten anchor banks became nine, because the CIMB Berhad acquired the Southern Bank Berhad in year 2006. The government reinforce the encouragement of merger and acquisition in the National Budget of 2006. The government provides exemption on stamp duty and real property gains tax for

companies undergoing merger and acquisition (My Sin Chew, 2008). Currently, in year 2011, there are eight anchor banks as the Eon Bank Berhad had been acquired by Hong Leong Bank Berhad on October, 2011. The reduction of number of bank in Malaysia since year 1980s is show in the Table 2.

Table 2- Year and Number of Bank in Malaysia

YEAR	NUMBER OF BANK
<i>Before Economic Recession in mid of 1980 :</i>	
1980	80
<i>After Economic Recession in mid of 1980 :</i>	
1990	79
<i>After Asian Financial Crisis :</i>	
1997	73
1999	54
<i>After Central Bank Proposed Major Restructuring Plan in February 2000 :</i>	
2003	10
2006	9
2011	8

(Source: Central Bank of Malaysia, 1980-2011)

Problem Statement

Malaysian Government encourages merger and acquisition in the country since the financial crisis in year 1997. Government introduces new plan and rule in order to encourage merger and acquisition in Malaysia. Additionally, Malaysian Government also provides several incentives such as free stamp duty and tax exemption for companies undergoing merger and acquisition. During year 1999, Central Bank of Malaysia proposed a major restructuring plan, Financial Sector Master Plan (FSM) for its fifty four domestic deposit-taking financial institutions to be consolidated into just ten anchor banks. Government believes larger and better-capitalized banking groups are more competitive and efficient. Therefore, they will be able to meet the challenges of a liberalized market place.

Besides that, the government of Malaysia reinforces the encouragement of merger and acquisition during year 2006. According to the Income Tax Act, the government provides tax incentive to merger companies with requirement which must be listed in the Bursa Malaysia. For instance, the target company will not have any balancing charge or

deductible balancing allowance arising from the merger and acquisition. In addition, the bidder company also is deemed to have acquired the assets at its tax written down value. As a result, this will increase the deductible capital allowance and decrease the tax payable. Moreover, according to the Stamp Duty Act, stamp duty exemption is given on an approved scheme of merger and acquisition undertaken by companies listed on Bursa Malaysia.

The encouragement of merger and acquisition in banking industry by the government was being the issue of many previous researchers. But, it is still not able to prove that whether the government is on or off the right path. Most of the previous researchers found merger and acquisition could reduce the operating cost, gaining market share and increase the competitive advantages (Terjesen, 2009). However, some researchers also found that merger and acquisition fail due to lack of control. This may because the size of company is too large (Peter, 2008).

The present study is different from the previous because most of the previous researcher used Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA), CAMEL-types variables and case study.

But, the results of previous studies are inconsistent, which mean the outcome of the effort that Government spent in encouraging merger and acquisition is still vague. If the current incentives provided by Government could not generate desired outcome, Government should think of other alternatives or terminate the encouragement plan. This is because the encouragement such as incentive given will increase the government expenses; tax exemption will reduce government income. Hence, the failure in this issue will affect the financial health of the country.

Hence, this study will focus on the capital structure before and after merger and acquisition of merged companies to determine whether merger and acquisition will bring benefit solely to companies and also the country's economic.

Research Objective

- (1) To investigate relationship between capital structure and performance of the bank before and after merger and acquisition.
- (2) To identify reasons of merger and acquisition.
- (3) To examine the consequences of merger and acquisition to the firm value of bank in Malaysia.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Capital Structure and Size of Company

In general, firm size has been empirically found to be strongly positively related to capital structure. (Kurshev and Strebulaev, 2006). These proved by Byoun (2007) studies two separate sizes of firm, firms with negative retained earnings (small firm) and positive retained earnings (large firm). The study found that there are strong and significant positive relationship between firm size and leverage ratio for firms with negative retained earnings. This study shows that smaller firms are more likely to issue equity financing and increase cash holdings despite having low leverage. In addition, Kurshev and Strebulaev (2006) found larger firm have larger leverage than smaller firm. This means large firm more intended to use debt financing because they enjoy cheaper external financing cost. On the other hand, smaller firm small leverage because more likely to short term debt (Booth et al., 2001).

However, Byoun (2007) found negative relationship between firm size and leverage ratio in the larger firm group. The regression model proves that larger firm will rely on the

internal fund so the leverage ratio is low. This fit to Pecking Order theory which explained that there are significant negative relationship between profit and debt, where positive relationship between tangibility asset and growth variable. Furthermore, Suhaila, Kila, Mahmood, and Mansor (2008) found there is negative relationship between firm size and capital structure. This study show that larger firm is less dependent on leverage financing compare to smaller firm. The larger firms much employ equity financing or utilized its retained earnings to finance its operation. So, the larger firms tend to have an optimal capital structure and will produce better performance.

In banking industry, Gropp and Heider (2009) study on capital structure of European banks show that large, publicly traded banks would have low leverage ratio and tend to hold more capital. The larger banks regularly show profit and pay dividend with high market to book ratio. So, it is able to equity at short period with lower cost. This similar to other industries that larger firm more rely on public debt so the leverage is low, while smaller firm tend to make bank loan so leverage ratio is high (Leary, 2005).

After merger and acquisition, banks will have more leverage and stronger capital structure. This is due to the increase in internal fund and cheaper external finance cost. So, banks would have higher cash balances and higher flow. Consequently, banks could provide more loans to public. This may cause the loan provided greater than the deposit received. Hence, the interest income derive from loan will be greater than the interest paid to depositors and increase profit to achieve better performance (Minton and Wruck, 2001). However, some banks would have lower leverage after merger. This may be caused by the bank only rely on the internal fund and equity financing such as retained earnings. Hence, both of the business and financial risk is low.

As a result, it is anticipated that size will affect capital structure of merger and acquisition.

Capital structure after merger and acquisition

According to Leland (2007), risk can be lowered via a merger or initial consolidation when activities' cash flows are imperfectly correlated. Lower risk reduces expected default costs. As a result, leverage can potentially be increased with greater tax benefits (Lewellen, 1971). As a general rule, the leverage effect is positive (negative) when the optimally levered merged firm has greater (lesser) debt

value than the sum of the separate optimally levered debt values.

Yang (2009) found bidder have lower leverage ratio compare to their target. This indicates the target is more likely to be facing financial problem, but still has opportunity to grow. Thus, the merger will help the bidder achieve the optimal capital structure. Optimal capital structure is based on the trade-off theory. Trade-off theory is a modern capital structure theory found by France Modigliani and Merton Miller in year 1958. The theory explains that large profitability firm would use debt financing and hence high leverage (Hackbarth, 2007). This is because firm wants to trade-off the tax benefit of debt financing against problems caused by potential bankruptcy (Brigham and Houston, 2007). Hence, optimal capital structure exists when the marginal cost equal to the marginal benefit of debt financing. The study found many firms achieved their target leverage ratios by acquiring other firms and the capital structure will change after merger and acquisition. This study found that market reacts positively to the reduction in leverage deficit. Leverage deficit is defined as the difference between target leverage and lagged leverage. According to Huang and Ritter (2004), the static tradeoff theory predicts firms with a large leverage deficit will issue debt to adjust toward their target leverage. But, Uysal (2009) argue that managers of overleveraged firms will reduce leverage deficit and issue equity to mitigate the negative effects of overleveraged. Hence, Yang (2009) concludes that merger would cause the purchaser reduce leverage deficit and reduction in operating expense, which also drive to increase in earning and market to book ratio, this means that the firm value is maximize.

However, Vermaelen and Xu (2010) using data of 2,978 firms in US listed companies which merged and acquired between years 1980 to 2005, found that leverage is significantly and negatively related to proxy for growth opportunities. Furthermore, the study found a measure of profitability, return on assets (ROA), is negatively related to leverage. The study found that profitable firm will have highest firm value, hence they prefer low leverage.

Capital Structure to Assess Company Performance

The theory of the capital structure is an important reference theory in enterprise's financing policy. The capital structure referred to enterprise includes mixture of debt and equity financing Chow and Lee (2008). During year 1963, under considering the corporate taxes, Modigliani and Miller modified the conclusion to recognize tax shield. Because

debt can reduces the tax to pay, so the best capital structure of enterprises should be 100% of the debt. But this seems to be unreasonable in the real world. This study shows that capital structure choice is a trade-off between the costs and benefits of debt.

Moreover, based on a study on effect of capital structure on firm performance done by Chow and Lee (2008), the result shown a strong relation between return on equity (ROE) and the debt-to-assets ratio (DTA). This means high leverage company will have higher performance. In consistent to this, Akintoye (2008) also found that capital structure has significant relationship with the performance. The study found that the strong capital structure company will has high performance because investors have more trust and confidence in the company which owns strong capital structure.

In addition, Margaritis and Psillaki (2008) studied on Korean companies. The result proved company performance efficiency on leverage is positive relationship. This consistent to Milken (2009), which mean higher leverage company have strong capital structure. Hence, the company has enough funds to reinvest and generate its operation. As a result, the company is able to increase its performance.

Strong capital structure will drove to good company performance (Milken 2009). Milken (2009) found when balance sheets began to improve and corporations with strong capital structures, company will start acquiring others. As a result, the sufficient fund enables company to widen their investment and operation. In return, it will increase the company performance and also shareholders wealth. Since capital structure may help stakeholders to assess the ability of company to cover the financial risk that it is running. Hence, they could determine the company's performance based on the capital structure. (Porteous and Tapadar, 2008).

METHODOLOGY

Sample

The sample data use in this study is seven cases from the six anchor banks in Malaysia. This is because Malaysian Central Bank initially encouraged local banks to merge after the world financial crisis in year 1997. Moreover, Malaysia government reinitiated a robust bank merger programme to restructure the Malaysian banks in year 1999 (Yong, The Edge June 15, 2010). Furthermore, the anchor banks required minimum RM 2 billion of share capital and at least RM 25 million of assets base. The anchor banks was rushing to meet their deadlines of signing of the sale and purchase

agreement on 31st August 2000 and to complete their merger exercise by 31st December 2000. Out of the 10 anchor banks, six have completed their mergers while three are in final stages of completion.

(AlphaInvestmentBank.com). According to Bank Negara Malaysia (January 28, 2002), banking institutions which had not achieved this minimum capitalization by 31 December 2001 would be in contravention of Section 14 of the Banking and Financial Institutions Act 1989 (BAFIA). However, to ensure that there is no disruption to banking services and to protect the interest of the public, a six-month

extension until 30 June 2002 granted to the banking institutions to comply with Section 14 of the BAFIA.

In year 2006, one of the ten anchor banks in Malaysia, Southern Bank Berhad acquired by the CIMB Bank Berhad. Hence, the number of Malaysian anchor banks reduced to nine. Recently, there are eight anchor banks left in Malaysia as the Hong Leong Bank acquires EON Bank Berhad in mid of year 2011. Hence, this study examines seven cases from six of the anchor banks shown in Table 3 exclude RHB and Affin Bank Berhad.

Table 3- List of Sample Malaysian Anchor Banks

1. Maybank Berhad	2. CIMB Berhad
3. Public Bank Berhad	4. Alliance Bank Malaysia Berhad
5. AmBank (M) Berhad	6. Hong Leong Bank Berhad
7. RHB Bank Berhad	8. Affin Bank Berhad

(Source: Central Bank of Malaysia, 2011)

3.3 Data Covered

The data use in this study is gathered from the annual report of all target and bidder banks of this seven cases which shown in Table 4. The data divided into pre and post of merger and acquisition for the descriptive equality test analysis. The data collected is according to the year of each

individual bank's completed merger and acquisition. Hence, the data covered five years before and after the merger and acquisition completed. The year of merger and acquisition completed of each sample bank shown in Table 4. Furthermore, analysis carried out on a five years pre-merger and five years post-merger period.

Table 4- Year of Merger and Acquisition of Each Malaysian Anchor Bank

Anchor Banks	Bank Merged/Acquired	Year Merged/ Acquired
1. Maybank Berhad	The Pacific Bank – <i>merged</i>	2000
2. CIMB Berhad	Bumiputra Commerce Berhad <i>acquired</i> Southern Bank Berhad (to formed CIMB Berhad)	2006

3. Alliance Bank (M) Berhad	Multi-Purpose Bank Bhd merged with - Sabah Bank Bhd (to formed Alliance Bank Malaysia Berhad)	2001
4. Alliance Bank (M) Berhad	Alliance Finance Berhad - <i>merged</i>	2004
5. AmBank (M) Berhad	Arab-Malaysian Finance Berhad and MBF Finance Berhad – <i>merged</i> (to form Am Bank (M) Berhad)	2002
6. Hong Leong Bank Berhad	Hong Leong Finance (2001) - <i>merged</i>	2001
7. Public Bank Berhad	Hock Hua Bank – <i>merged</i>	2001

(Source: Central Bank of Malaysia, 2011)

3.4 Method

Most of the previous studies on efficiency of merger and acquisition in Malaysian banks were carried out using Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA). DEA was first introduced by Charnes et al. (1978) to measure the efficiency of each Decision Making Units (DMUs) that is obtained as a maximum of a ratio of weighted outputs to weighted inputs. This denotes that the more the output produced from given inputs, the more efficient is the production. The weights for the ratio are determined by a restriction that the similar ratios for every DMU have to be less than or equal to unity. Sufian and Fadzlan (2004) study the merger and acquisition of Malaysian Banks from 1998-2003 by using Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA). The study shows the small and medium size banks have benefited the most from merger compare to large banks. Moreover, Noormala et al. (2011) were conducting questionnaire survey to 43 successful merger and acquisition firms. The result show merger and acquisition will bring improvement of profitability and formation of economies of scale. However, the DEA is less data demanding. Hence, it does not accurately interfere the whole population. (Sufian and Fadzlan, 2004).

However, Rasidah et al. (2008) use CAMEL-types variables to study the efficiency effect on merger and acquisition. CAMEL-type variables include capital buffer ratio, loan

growth, loan loss reserve, cost efficiency, interest earning ratio and loan deposit ratio. CAMEL-type variables reflect not only the soundness of a bank's management but also its profitability (ROE). The model is examining the effect of CAMEL-type variables to the profitability (ROE). The results suggest that the mergers did not seem to enhance the productive efficiency of the banks as they do not indicate any significant difference.

The previous studies are still unable to prove the decisions about merger and acquisition made by government completely suit the companies' objective and economic benefits. We are still vague about effect of merger and acquisition. So, to distinguish this paper from the existing literature, this paper will focus alone on the changes of capital structure as a result of merger and acquisition of banking sector in Malaysia. This is because capital structure is an important issue in corporate finance (Yang, 2009). Capital structure is mix of debt and equity the firm uses to finance its operations (Brigham and Houston, 2007).

This paper uses capital structure to measure the performance of the bidder and target bank before and after merger and acquisition. In finance, capital structure refers to the way a corporation finances its assets through some combination of equity, debt, or hybrid securities (Saad, 2010). According to Loth (2006), the strength of a company's balance sheet can be evaluated by three broad categories of investment-quality

measurements working capital adequacy, asset performance and capital structure. Furthermore, Loth (2006) states that a healthy proportion of equity capital in a company's capital structure is an indication of financial fitness. Usually, investors are favour to company with good fundamentals which is a strong balance sheet. Investors would pay attention and rely on the companies' financial statement for investing decision.

Moreover, in the perspective of Willcocks (2008), share price is a fundamental barometer of corporate performance, and one that is communicated to customers, shareholders and suppliers equally. Moreover, the fluctuation of share price can determine the improvement or declination of company performance. For instance, when a company performance is good, the share price will also increase directly and hence the shareholder return and return on equity will high (Kester, 2004).

3.5 Variables Determinant

In this study two main groups of variables are identified, which are capital structure (independent variable) and company performance (dependent variable). Capital structure refers to total debt ratio (TDR), debt to equity ratio (DTE), and interest coverage ratio (ICR). Where the ratios will be use to represent the company performance are return on equity (ROE), return on assets (ROA) and earnings per share (EPS). These research variables are summarized in Table 5.

Total Debt Ratio (TDR)

Capital structure is more appropriate to define by using total debt ratio. Moreover, debt ratio is employed to explain the amount of leverage used by a company to finance its assets (Suhaila et al., 2008). Total debt ratio is defined as total debts which included long term and short term debts divided by total assets of the firm. When the percentage of the debt ratio is high, this means the company is riskier to be default in payment but, it may also help the company to generate high return. In other words, high risk high returns (Brigham and Houston, 2007).

Debt to Equity Ratio (DTE)

The second variable that will be used is debt to equity ratio. Debt to equity indicates the portion of debt the company is using to finance its asset with respect to shareholders equity. Debt to equity ratio is defined as long-term debt divided by total shareholders' equity. Same as total debt ratio, the

higher debt to equity (higher leverage) indicate that company has been aggressive in financing its growth with debt. Company used debt than equity because they have tax interest in paying the interest on debt, hence they would have additional cash to generate higher return in their business. (Nissim and Penman, 2001)

Interest Coverage Ratio (ICR)

Interest coverage ratio is used to measure the extent to which operating income can decline before the firm is unable to meet its annual interest cost. Interest coverage ratio is defined as earnings before interest and tax (EBIT) of the firm divided by the interest payment (Brigham and Houston, 2007). According to (Suhaila, Kila and Mansor, 2008), the lower interest coverage ratio indicates high leverage because the firm was borrowing addition for investment in order to generate high return. However, high interest coverage ratio means that the business will be able to meet its interest obligations from profits easily.

Return on Assets (ROA)

Furthermore, return on assets (ROA) will be used to determine the performance of banks. Return on assets is defined as net income divided by total assets. This ratio is use to measure how much profit the company can generated with each dollar of assets. The higher ROA indicate the company is performing well. (Brigham and Houston, 2007)

Return on Equity (ROE)

In addition, return on equity (ROE) is defined as net income divided by common equity. ROE is used to identify the shareholders' return. This also indicates the management's performance. (Brigham and Houston, 2007). The higher the ROE means the surplus funds can be invested to improve business operations without having additional investment of capital from shareholders (Graham, Zweig and Buffett, 2003).

Earnings per Share (EPS)

Besides, earnings per share (EPS) indicate how much earnings has been generated per share of stock during the reported period. As a firms earnings increase, earnings per share looks better and the firm releasing more shares increases the number of shares outstanding (Gyimah and Oscar, 2011). Earnings per share can be determined as net

income divided by total number of share outstanding (Brigham and Houston, 2007).

Table 5- Summary of Research Variables

Research Variables	Authors
(A) Independent Variables: Capital Structure	
(1) Total debt ratio = $\frac{\text{Total debts}}{\text{Total assets}}$	Suhaila, Kila, Mahmood, and Mansor (2008) Brigham and Houston (2007)
(2) Debt to equity ratio = $\frac{\text{Long term debts}}{\text{Total shareholders' equity}}$	Nissim and Penman. (2001)
(3) Interest coverage ratio = $\frac{\text{Earnings before interest and tax (EBIT)}}{\text{Interest payment}}$	Suhaila, Kila, Mahmood, and Mansor (2008) Brigham and Houston (2007)
(B) Dependent Variables: Company Performance	
(1) Return on assets = $\frac{\text{Net income}}{\text{Total assets}}$	Brigham and Houston (2007)
(2) Return on equity = $\frac{\text{Net income}}{\text{Common equity}}$	Brigham and Houston (2007) Graham, Zweig and Buffett (2003)
(3) Earnings per share = $\frac{\text{Net income}}{\text{Number of share outstanding}}$	Gyimah and Oscar (2011) Brigham and Houston (2007)
(C) Control Variables:	
(1) Size = Log Total Assets	Bouwman (2009)
(2) Relative size = $\frac{\text{Total assets of target}}{\text{Total assets of bidder}}$	Altunbas and David (2004)
(3) Bidder performance = return on equity (ROE) of bidder (Pre-merger) $= \frac{\text{Net income}}{\text{Common equity}}$	Altunbas and David (2004)

Hypotheses

The hypotheses of this study are:

Hp1: There are relationship between return on assets (ROA) and independent variables.

Hp2: There are relationship between return on equity (ROE) and independent variables.

Hp3: There are relationship between earnings per share (EPS) and independent variables.

DATA ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

Analysis of Regression Before Eliminating Debt to Equity (DTE) and Relative Size (RSIZE)

The regression analysis was performed to test the impact of financial performance on capital structure before and after merger and acquisition of the Malaysian anchor banks. The period of sample data in the regression analysis is 5 years before the merger and acquisition and 5 years after the merger and acquisition took place. Table 6 to 9 present the results of regressing the bank performance before and after the merger and acquisition while controlling for other factors that may affect operating performance. As explained

in chapter 3, these other factors include size, relative size and bidder performance.

Table 6 and 7 indicate the result of the regression of pre and post-merger of Malaysian banks. According to the un-standardized coefficient (un-standardize B) in the regression model of return on assets (ROA), noted that the debt to equity (DTE) is highly correlated to the total debt ratio (TDR) and the relative size of bidder and target (RSIZE) is highly correlated to the size of bank (SIZE). Since the result of T-significant of DTE (64.6%) and RSIZE (90.9%) are not significant compared to TDR (45%) and SIZE (0.1%), so DTE and RSIZE are eliminated and the regression was rerun.

Table 6- Summary of Regression Result (T-statistics) without Eliminate DTE and RSIZE – Pre-Merger

Regression Model	Independent Variables					
	TDR	DTE	ICR	SIZE	RSIZE	B/PFM
ROA						
Unstandardized-B	-0.072	2.285E-005	0.008	0.061	-2.800E-005	0.001
T-Sig	0.045	0.646	0.155	0.001	0.909	0.220
ROE						
Unstandardized-B	-2.381	-0.021	-0.181	9.229	-0.059	0.556
T-Sig	0.751	0.049	0.877	0.013	0.265	0.000
EPS						
Unstandardized-B	0.000	0.000	0.024	0.194	-0.002	0.009
T-Sig	0.999	0.124	0.439	0.045	0.241	0.008

Table 7- Summary of Regression Result (T-statistics) without Eliminate DTE and RSIZE – Post-Merger

Independent	Independent Variables			
	TDR	DTE	ICR	SIZE
ROA				
Unstandardized-B	-0.001	-2.253E-005	-9.599E-005	0.004
T-Sig	0.810	0.002	0.655	0.067
ROE				
Unstandardized-B	1.934	-0.021	0.464	6.249
T-Sig	0.688	0.011	0.064	0.009
EPS				
Unstandardized-B	0.137	-0.001	0.011	0.230
T-Sig	0.389	0.003	0.190	0.004

4.2 Analysis of Regression After Eliminating Debt to Equity (DTE) and Relative Size (RSIZE)

4.2.1 Analysis of ANOVA

The new regression result of pre-merger stage and post-merger stage of Malaysian banks is shown in Table 8. According to the result of adjusted R-squared for return on assets (ROA), return on equity (ROE), and earning per share (EPS) in Table 8, there is only 27.5 % of ROA, 25.5% of ROE and 14.7% of EPS can be explained by total debt ratio (TDR), interest coverage ratio (ICR), size of bank (SIZE), and bidder performance (B/PFM) during the pre-merger stage. However, adjusted R-square has been improved during the post-merger (Table 8). During the post-merger stage, there are 52.6% of ROA, 45.3% of ROE and 45.6% of ICR can be explained by the TDR and ICR. The bidder performance (control variable) during the pre-merger pulled down the adjusted R-squared. This means the bidder performance unable to explain the dependent variables (ROA, ROE and EPS). This due to B/PFM defined as the ROE of bidder before merger and acquisition. Hence, B/PFM variable is equal to the performance variables. After merger and acquisition, the bidder performance is no longer in the regression model. Hence, the performance of bank can be explained more by the capital structure of the Malaysian bank.

4.2.2 Regression Result (T-significant) on Return on Assets

The new regression result of pre-merger stages of Malaysian banks is shown in Table 8 and 9. The result in Table 8 shows total debt ratio is negatively significantly to return on assets during the pre-merger stage. This is because

profitable firm will have highest firm value and hence prefer low leverage (Vermaelen and Xu, 2010). But, Table 9 shows that total debt ratio becomes positively significant to the return on assets during the post-merger stage. This is due to the fact that during pre-merger, banks which use more debt to finance it assets need to pay higher finance cost. So, the return on assets may pull down by the high finance cost. Furthermore, the result proves merger and acquisition may increase the credibility of firm and able to finance more at lower interest rate. Hence, the more leverage firm will able to generate higher return after merger and acquisition. This result is consistent to Chow and Lee, 2008 and the hypothesis 1, which state that total debt has positive relationship with return on assets.

In the context of interest coverage ratio, the result proves this ratio is insignificant to return on assets during both pre and post-merger stages. This indicates there is not clear relationship between interest coverage and return on asset. This means bank with better return on asset is not necessary able to pay its interest more effectively. This may due to the higher financing cost may pull down the net income of the bank. Another reason is ability to pay the interest is depending on the cash that the bank holds and not depends solely on the net income. This oppose to the hypothesis 1, which state that interest coverage has significant relationship with return on assets.

The result shows size (control variable) of bank is positively significant to the return on assets, but it becomes insignificant after merger and acquisition. The possible reason for this is larger bank able to generate higher return due to sufficient assets during pre-merger and acquisition. After merger and acquisition, when the size become too large or over a certain limit, the conflict between

management and lost of management control may caused inefficient in return on assets (Allen and Boobal, 2005). On the other hand, some banks able to maintain a good internal control and assets management will increase the efficiency after merger and acquisition. In addition, some banks will become smaller after merger and acquisition due to disposal of asset, where some will become bigger due to consolidation of asset. Hence, there does not have a clear relationship between size and return on assets after merger and acquisition.

The result provides bidder performance (control variable) is insignificant to return on assets. This is because the bidder performance is the return on equity of bidder bank and which cannot determine the return on assets.

4.2.3 Regression Result (T-significant) on Return on Equity

Table 8 and 9 also show that total debt ratio is insignificant to the return on equity during pre-merger stage. This is because prior to the merger and acquisition, the bank's condition may affect the relationship of total debt ratio and return on equity. This means some banks with high leverage will increase the debt services through expensive finance cost, which will lower the income available to shareholders. Besides, there are banks which have high leverage able to generate high return and return on equity. This may due to bank able to finance at lower cost due to characteristic of company and relationship with creditor. So, there is not a fixed relationship between total debt ratio and return on equity. However, total debt turned positively and highly significant to return on equity after merger and acquisition. This indicates merger and acquisition most probably may help banks to finance their operation with external finance sources at cheapest interest cost (Minton and Wruck, 2001). The sufficient fund enables banks to invest more in operation and expand their services. According to Minton and Wruck (2001), who documented bank with high cash balances could provide more loans to public. This may caused the loan provided greater than the deposit received, and interest income derive from loan would greater than the interest paid to depositors. Hence, the bank performance will improve and shareholders' return will directly increase. This consistent to the hypothesis 2, which stated total debt ratio has relationship to the return on equity.

The interest coverage ratio is insignificant to return on equity before and after merger and acquisition. As the result regression model of return on assets, interest coverage does not have definite relationship between interest coverage and

return on equity. This determines the performance of banks may not be able to determine by ability to repay the interest. This is because better performance bank may involve in provide variety of loan services to customer. Hence, they keep reinvest their income and may lack of cash to repay their interest. However, sometimes bank which has lower performance but stronger asset management system may more able to repay the interest compare to the better performance bank. The possible reason for this is relationship between interest coverage and return on equity may depend on other external factor. These results inconsistent to the hypothesis 2 which state that interest coverage have significant relationship with the return on equity.

The result in Table 8 and 9 prove that size (control variable) is positively significant to return on equity during both pre and post merger and acquisition. One reason could be size can determined by the return on equity. This explains larger bank able to generate highest return on equity. After merger and acquisition, the increase in size of the bank will drive up the performance and return on equity. This may because investor will be more confident to invest in the bank after merger and acquisition. Thus, bank has more sufficient internal fund to generate the operation and higher income through reduce in paying the expensive finance cost (Minton and Wruck, 2001). In addition, the bidder performance is positively highly significant to the return on equity because the bidder performance also represent the return on equity of bank. This also proved by the correlation (+1).

4.2.4 Regression Result (T-significant) on Earning per Share

Result in Table 8 proves that total debt ratio, interest coverage ratio, size, and earning per share did not have significant relationship during the pre-merger stage. This define earning per share cannot determined by the leverage ratios and size during pre-merger stage in Malaysian anchor bank context. But, Table 9 shows that total debt ratio, interest coverage ratio and size are positively significantly with earning per share after the merger and acquisition. This means after merger and acquisition, if the bidder and target bank consolidate all the assets, the size of bank will become larger than before. This will increase the confident of creditors and shareholders to the bank. Hence, creditors able to offer fund at cheapest interest rate due to the default risk is low and shareholder will more interested to invest in the bank. Hence, bank will have more sufficient to expand the operation. Thus, earning per share will increased through the

increase in performance and net income after merger and acquisition. This consistent to the hypothesis 3, which states that total debt ratio, interest coverage ratio and size have positive relationship to earning per share. Moreover, Table 8

proves the bidder performance (control variable) is positively significant to the earning per share. This is due to the fact that increased in return on equity will also increased the shareholder's return (earning per share).

Table 8- Summary of Regression Result (T-statistics) after Eliminate DTE and RSIZE – Pre-Merger

Variables	Regression on Return on Assets (ROA)	Regression on Return on Equity (ROE)	Regression on Earning per Share (EPS)
Intercept	-0.442 (0.001)***	-58.697 (0.029)**	-0.814 (0.242)
Total Debt Ratio (TDR)	-0.073 (0.037)**	0.810 (0.991)	0.002 (0.990)
Interest Coverage Ratio (ICR)	0.008 (0.129)	-1.900 (0.872)	0.330 (0.279)
Size (SIZE)	0.061 (0.000)***	8.227 (0.024)**	0.150 (0.091)
Bidder Performance (B/PFM)	-0.001 (0.192)	1.348 (0.000)***	0.054 (0.003)***
Adjusted R ²	0.275	0.255	0.147

Note: *** significant at 1% level

** significant at 5% level

Table 9 - Summary of Regression Result (T-statistics) after Eliminate DTE and RSIZE –Post-Merger

Variables	Regression on Return on Assets (ROA)	Regression on Return on Equity (ROE)	Regression on Earning per Share (EPS)
Intercept	-0.008 (0.483)	-25.790 (0.096)	-1.518 (0.006)***
Total Debt Ratio (TDR)	0.006 (0.000)***	6.648 (0.000)***	0.180 (0.001)***
Interest Coverage Ratio (ICR)	0.001 (0.485)	3.241 (0.129)	0.198 (0.009)***
Size (SIZE)	0.001 (0.192)	0.591 (0.000)***	0.010 (0.003)***
Adjusted R ²	0.526	0.453	0.456

Note: *** significant at 1% level

** significant at 5% level

Changes in Capital Structure

Based on the comparison between capital structure ratios for the pre and post-merger and acquisition (Table-10), the result shows that there is slightly increased in the mean of total debt ratio TDR) (81.60 per cent vs 101.20 per cent). This also validated by the insignificant T-test (TDR-ROA: 65.5%, TDR-ROE: 77.3% and TDR-EPS: 26.5%; critical value=5%) of the mean ratio of changes before and after merger and acquisition in Table 10. This means, after the merger and acquisition, banks' leverage increased due to more funding available from debt to finance their asset. However, this will also increase the risk of default payment as the level of debt increases. Furthermore, this indicates that the creditors are more confidence with the performance of the banks after merger and acquisition and willing to provide more loans to the bank.

Table 10 displays the mean of interest coverage ratio (ICR) which shows significant increased (163.10 per cent vs 268.10 per cent) after merger and acquisition. Table 11

indicates the T-significant of the changes of ICR to ROA (0%), ROE (0%) and EPS (1.1%). This proved the significant changes of ICR after the merger and acquisition at the 5% significant level. This indicates that the ability of banks to meet its interest obligations from profits and the total debt ratio of the bank are increased. This is due to the fact that after merger and acquisition, banks able to enjoy cheaper interest loan. Creditors will more confident with the bank after merger and acquisition. This is because the growth of company asset and reputation reduced the default risk that bank unable to repay the debt. Hence, creditors able to offer debt in lower interest rate.

From the debt to equity ratio (DTE) perspective, the mean value has declined (1928.06 per cent vs 1671.18 per cent), this is because the increased of share capital is greater than the increased in debt after merger and acquisition. Moreover, this is due to the fact that bank able to generate more cash to satisfy the debt obligation. This increases credibility of bank and causes total debt ratio increased. The reason is when the bank is more credible, it may more easy to get loan from external creditor because the risk of default payment is low.

Changes in Performance

Results of Table 10 show a significant increased in the mean of return on asset (ROA) (-2.00 per cent vs 0.90 per cent). This also verified by the highly significant F-test (0%) as in Table 11. The due to the fact that bank is able to generate higher return with each dollar of asset after merger and acquisition. This because merger and acquisition may help banks to reduce the fixed cost by removing the duplicate operation departments and achieve economics of scale. For instance, bank may close down some branches after merger and acquisition to reduce the operating cost. Hence, this could increase the income through reduction in operating cost. Merger and acquisition potentially pull up the ability of banks involved in diversifying their businesses. This could be due to the fact that consolidation of variety assets allowed bank to provide variety of services, investments and loan packages. In addition, this may enable bank to gain higher growth and new customers. For instance, after merger and acquisition commercial bank not only able to provide the overdraft but also mortgage loan to customers. Moreover, bank also may upgrades and invests in customer friendly technology such as internet banking and other loan repayment system. The advanced system may improve the customer experiences and satisfactions. This result also consistent to Gadiesh and Ormiston (2002), the study found merger and acquisition could broadening scope and redefining the business.

With regard to return on equity, the mean value (512.60 per cent vs 1080.40 per cent) also rose significantly after the merger and acquisition. This validated by significant level (0.2%) of the F-test in Table 11. The possible reason of this is improvement of managements' performance. Hence, banks have surplus funds for reinvest to improve business operations without having additional investment of capital from shareholders. Since management of banks are making up from talent and expert in different field, thus after the merger and acquisition, management of bidder and target bank may share and exchange their knowledge to enhance the management and banks performance. Another reason could be equity increased after merger and acquisition, banks may able to invest more in more productive investment and generate higher return which will again pull up the ROE.

The mean value of earning per share (EPS) is dropped slightly (46.70 per cent vs 34.40 per cent). The F-test of EPS (3.8%) in Table 11 proves the insignificant decrease after the merger and acquisition. This may caused by the

increased in number of share greater than the increased in net income. As the numbers of share has positive relationship with the shareholders' equity, so, when the increased in shareholders' equity is greater than the increased in debt, DTE will drop. One can argue that after merger and acquisition the banks are further more likely to finance externally due to the lowest interest rate offered. The reason that increased in income is lesser due to the payment of interest expense to creditors. On the other hand, the number of share increased may due to shareholder more confident that bank potentially to growth and increase the investment onto the banks.

The result reveals that the size (total assets) of bank increased slightly by 3.778% (Table 10) after merger and acquisition. This is consistent with the result of Kurshev and Strebulaev (2006), that the firm size has positive relationship with the capital structure. This could due to the fact that increases in the gap between original size of bidder and target before merger and acquisition of Malaysian bank is relatively small. Therefore, it does not bring huge changes of the banks' size even after merger and acquisition have taken place. Since, the size of bank in this study is presented by the total assets, after consolidation of the total asset of big bank (bidder) and a medium bank (target), the account of consolidated total asset only will slightly pull up by the total asset of bidder. In some cases, the bidder bank did not absorb 100% of the total assets of target bank during the merger and acquisition and the portion of the total assets will be disposed and distributed among bidder's shareholders before the merger and acquisition.

From the overall perspective, capital structure of Malaysian bank has not much increased after merger and acquisition. This presented by the TDR and ICR slightly increased by 24.02% and 64.38% while DTE decreased by 13.32%. The finding indicates that the increase in debt is lesser than the increase in shareholder equity after the merger and acquisition. This due to the fact that shareholders more confident and increase their investment to Malaysian bank after merger and acquisition. Shareholders believed after merger and acquisition, banks able to reduce competition, share resources, skills and experience which would enhance the efficiency (Bank Negara Malaysia, 2002). Moreover, bank could reduce the external fund when internal fund is sufficient to finance their operation. The result consistent with Minton and Wruck (2001), who documented the higher leverage level and stronger capital structure after merger and acquisition of banks. This proves that Malaysian banks have more internal funds to invest in their operation after the merger and acquisition. Simultaneously, the growth in

performance may drive up the ability of bank to meet the interest obligation and increase the ICR.

The result of profitability ratios (ROA and ROE) are presented in Table 10. The improvement of the profitability ratios after merger and acquisition implies the high leverage and good capital structure (increase in TDR) after merger and acquisition of Malaysian banks. This finding is in line with Chow and Lee (2008), Peter (2008) and Sufian and Habibullah (2009), who documented the improvement of operating performance and profitability after merger and acquisition. Merger and acquisition in Malaysian banking industries may improve technical efficiency and competitive advantages and hence higher return. However, the result of this paper oppose to the Vermaelen and Xu (2010), who proved after the merger and acquisition of US listed company, return on assets is negatively associated to leverage. The result of Vermaelen and Xu (2010) is similar to the Nigerian bank. In their studies, The Nigerian banks do not significantly improve the performance after merger and

acquisition. According to Amer et al., (2002), the changes of performance after merger and acquisition may depend on the countries' economic environment.

Although the results of ROA and ROE improved, but the EPS dropped after the merger and acquisition of Malaysian bank. This may caused by the increase in number of share is much greater than the increase in net income after merger and acquisition. This paper found that merger and acquisition of Malaysian banks will slightly improve the capital structure and performance. Furthermore, this paper also supports that the merger and acquisition will improve the banks performance. This is because the merger and acquisition reduces the intense competition of banking industry in Malaysia.

From the comprehensive view, this paper implies the only slight improvement in banks' performance after merger and acquisition. Therefore, it is of paramount importance for this study to shed some light to the policymakers in continuing the encouragement of merger and acquisition in Malaysia.

Table 10- Mean of Pre and Post-merger and Acquisition Ratios

		Pre-merger (5 Years Average)	Post-merger (5 Years Average)	Percentage Of Changes
Total Debt Ratio	(TDR)	0.816	1.012	24.02
Debt to Equity	(DTE)	192.806	167.118	-13.323
Interest Coverage Ratio	(ICR)	1.631	2.681	64.378
Return on Asset	(ROA)	-0.020	0.009	145.000
Return on Equity	(ROE)	5.126	10.804	110.769
Earning Per Share	(EPS)	0.467	0.344	-26.338
Size	(SIZE)	7.385	7.664	3.778

Table 11- Summary Regression Result (T-significant) of Changes between Pre and Post-merger and Acquisition Ratios

Variables	Regression on Return on Assets (ROA)	Regression on Return on Equity (ROE)	Regression on Earning per Share (EPS)
Intercept	- 0.009 (0.000)***	-3.531 (0.446)	-0.135 (0.057)
Total Debt Ratio (TDR)	0.002 (0.655)	2.560 (0.773)	0.204 (0.265)
Interest Coverage Ratio (ICR)	0.024 (0.000)***	2.788 (0.000)***	0.338 (0.011)**
Size (SIZE)	0.011 (0.002)***	9.069 (0.224)	-0.135 (0.575)
Adjusted R ²	0.893	0.322	0.182
F-significant	0.000***	0.002***	0.038**

Note: *** significant at 1% level

** significant at 5% level

Analysis of Significant Changes Bank

According to Table 12, capital ratio and company performance of Multi-Purpose Bank Berhad showed a significant change. This proved by the total debt ratio (TDR: 29.8 per cent vs 92.6 per cent), interest coverage ratio (ICR: 155.6% per cent vs 979.6 per cent), return on assets (ROA: -3 per cent vs 6 per cent), and return on equity (ROE: -930.8 per cent vs 833.4 per cent). This is because the Multi-Purpose Bank Berhad merged with seven banks at one time in year 2001 when the Central Bank of Malaysia encourage the stronger bank to merge and acquire smaller bank and reduce the fifty four banks to ten anchor banks. Multi-Purpose is named as one of the ten anchor banking group in the consolidation exercise for Malaysian financial institutions. During year 2001, in order to comply with the Malaysian government requirement for anchor bank, Multi-Purpose merged with International Bank Malaysia Berhad, Bolton Finance Berhad, Bumiputra Merchant Bankers Berhad, Sabah Bank Berhad, and Amanah Merchant Bank Berhad.

Table 12 displays the TDR and ICR of Multi-Purpose Bank Berhad which raised by 210.138% and 529.563% after the merger and acquisition where the DTE is dropped by 81.0811% due to strongly rely on external fund (increase in TDR). The heavily increased in the capital structure of course will pull up the profitability of the company. This validated by the 300% increase in ROA and 189.536% increase in ROE of Multi-Purpose Bank Berhad after the merger and acquisition. Moreover, the significant improved in leverage and performance of Multi-Purpose Bank also may cause by the economic condition. The Chart 1 indicates the growing of Malaysia Gross Domestic Product (GDP) after year 2001 (merger of Multi-Purpose Bank) until 2008. During economic growth, people intends to make loan and invests and this will drive up the interest rate and hence the performance of bank. Another reason is the existence of sufficient internal fund, cheap external finance cost after the merger and support from the economic condition drive up the ability of Multi-Purpose to diversify and expand the services provided to generate higher income.

Source: Malaysia Official's Statistic (2012)

However, the result shown that the size of Multi-Purpose Banks which measured by total assets of bank is slightly decreased by 8.189%. This may because Multi-Purpose Bank Berhad in used large amount of cash base payment to pay the bidder for the merger activity. Hence, the cash payment will reduce the asset and size of the bank. Moreover, according to Table 12, the size of Sabah Bank Berhad became smaller after merging with the Multi-Purpose Bank Berhad. Prior to the merger of Sabah Bank Berhad and Multi-Purpose Bank Berhad, Sabah Bank owned huge amount of total asset (about 27 billion) compared to Multi-Purpose Bank Berhad (about 15 million).

Based on the ratio changes of Sabah Bank Berhad after the merger and acquisition, it may conclude that Sabah Bank Berhad rarely used external fund to finance its business prior to the merger and acquisition. This prove by the much lower of DTE and ICR during pre-merger stage compare to post-merger (DTE: +197.256%, ICR: +625.63%). The small capital of Sabah Bank Berhad only sufficient to provide limited service and not allowed the bank to expand the business and this prove by the great improved of ROE (+4,173.846%) after the merger and acquisition. Hence, the EPS of Sabah Bank during the pre-merger stage also much

st-merger due to limited income on the pre-merger stage.

During the pre-merger period, TDR of Bumiputra Commerce Bank Berhad (bidder) is 91.6%. It is much higher compare to the TDR of Southern Bank (target) 16.4% (Table 12). This indicates Bumiputra Commerce highly relies on the external fund during the pre-merger. Whereas Southern Bank Berhad is more rely on the internal fund during the pre-merger stage. This fact due to Southern Bank Berhad is a large bank and has sufficient fund to operate the business. This fact contributed to the significant changes of TDR (+454.268%) and slender changes in the profitability ratio after merged with Bumiputra Commerce Bank Berhad. After the merger, the internal fund of Southern Bank shared in the group. Hence, the TDR of Bumiputra Commerce slightly dropped by 0.764% after the merger.

Furthermore, Alliance Bank Berhad also faced significant changes on the capital structure and performance after the merger and acquisition with Alliance Finance Berhad on year 2004. The TDR, ICR, ROA, and ROE of Alliance Bank are increased significantly. On the other hand, the Alliance Finance only showed significant improved on the profitability ratios (ROA, ROE and EPS). This may because Alliance Bank able to finance external to diversify the

services provided. For instance, Alliance Bank only provides deposit services, while Alliance Finance provides loans to customer. After merger and acquisition, Alliance Bank provides comprehensive services to clients such as variety type of deposits, mortgage loans, and investment accounts. This support Gadiesh and Ormiston (2002), the merger of compliment business may help the company achieve economic of scale. This may increase the source of income of the bank and hence drove up the profitability ratios of Alliance Bank.

Moreover, the MBF Finance Berhad also proves significant improved in the capital structure and profitability. The DTE and ICR increased by 662.443% and 178.25% respectively during the post-merger stage. Besides, the ROA, ROE and EPS of MBF Finance Berhad increased by 101.224%, 692.683% and 143.478%. The negative DTE, ICR, ROA, and EPS of MBF Finance during the pre-merger proves that MBF Finance is facing financial problem but still have opportunity to growth. This is consistent to the result of Yang (2009). MBF Finance Berhad facing the financial problem since the Asian financial crisis in year 1997 and dot com bust in year 2000. Consequently, the Arab Malaysia which has more strong capital structure merged with MBF Finance and formed AM Bank Group. Hence, the performance of both bidder and target banks are improve after the merger and acquisition.

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Table 12 displays the significant improved in ICR of the Hock Hua Bank Berhad after merger with the Public Bank Berhad. However, the other leverage and profitability ratios did not shown significant improvement. But, there are declined in profitability ratios compare to the pre-merger stage. This may because after merged with Public Bank Berhad, the bank able to obtain lower interest external fund due to the increase in size and the reputation of Public Bank. Besides, Table 12 proved that Hock Hua Bank solely has better performance than Public Bank Berhad during the pre-merger and post-merger stage.

Conclusion

The overall result proved that there are not an absolute significant relationship between all the independent variables and dependent variables. Moreover, there are not much increment in the leverage ratios and performance of the Malaysian banks after merger and acquisition. The size of Malaysian banks also did not increase significantly during the post-merger stage. This may caused by the economic condition in Malaysia as found by Amer, et al. (2002). The study stated different country has different economic condition and the economic condition will affect the performance after the merger and acquisition.

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